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the laptops, as opposed to stimulating economic growth in the respective developing country through subsidies and contracts to their local manufacturers. Furthermore, Warschauer (2010) discredited OLPC as a digression from more potent and urgent interventions to solve the poverty and illiteracy pandemic. Warschauer (2010) accused OPLC of ignoring the underlying cultural, infrastructural, and socioeconomic context in developing countries.

Disregarding incentives that ensure immediate sustainability, such as water, buildings, and streets, OLPC instead allocated much-needed funds to these laptops, whose efficacy have only been proven in moderate areas.

regional, and federal levels. Intel conceived this program as part of its social responsibility portfolio, for which the company has received critical acclaim and a spot among the world's top corporate citizens (Burton, 2011).

Briefly united with OLPC, Intel's program has pursued a similar agenda, yet distinguished itself through the provision of training and curriculum development to integrate the technologies optimally; on the other hand, OLPC was designed as a stand-alone gift to children.

In this way, *World Ahead* is more of a complete E-Learning solution than a laptop distribution program, partnering similarly with the local and federal stakeholders to devise a unique solution for each community. Intel has also relied on a broad, varied pool for funding and contributes \$100 million a year from its own assets to *World Ahead*. The *Classmate* laptop PC represents Intel's homegrown response to the XO with related specs and feats (Burton, 2011).

Beside Intel's *World Ahead*, other one-to-one laptop and related charitable E-Learning programs have been pioneered and rolled out throughout North and South America. In fact, Hawaii's *Laptops for Learning* program, initiated in 2000, represents a grant program to lease and/or purchase laptops for entire classes designed to thereby optimize learning for the individual and the community

This program coordinated with parents, students, teachers, administrators, and various levels of government to ensure a decent experience (Kennedy; Severin; 2011).

Furthermore, The State of Michigan founded the Michigan Virtual University in 1998 as an online supplement to its K-12 school system. The program rolled out a series of low-cost and free web-based professional development courses, as well as an innovative, ambitious research consortium to offer multilateral support to Michigan's school system.

The State of Maine carried a related incentive, the Maine Learning Technology Initiative

Background and Programs Related to OLPC

OLPC exists alongside related programs, such as Intel's *World Ahead* program and various prior initiatives and developments at the local,

(MLTI), seeking to embed technology in the curriculum and connect students. One-to-one laptop initiatives have up to the present permeated the Caribbean and Latin-American realm, ranging from Brazil to Nicaragua. Indeed, One-to-one laptop programs and the OLPC have saturated the globe, leaking even into Nepal and Rwanda (Kennedy; Severin; 2011).

Working Definition

The OLPC program designates itself as a laptop production and distribution service for a low-income demographic, primarily targeting developing second-and third world countries. OLPC has set forth an elaborate, philanthropic mission statement to administer and justify its agenda, drawing from colonial and post-colonial theories and criticism that empowers individuals and envisions participation in a global information economy.

The OLPC mission is relatively straightforward and at least theoretically beneficial, yet critics emphasized the lack of

correlation of the proposed theory with the prevalent conditions in severely dilapidated third-world countries. Current research emphasizes that beneficial results from the program limit themselves to second-world countries and regions with at least basically functional infrastructures (Ezumah, 2010).

A program evaluation should consider that OLPC neither directly endorses or collaborates with any ancillary software or E-Learning provider, nor does it segue with an educational approach or ideology. This avoidance of a coherent implementation strategy has incurred criticism from program evaluators.

Although OLPC had envisioned the XO laptop to encourage individualized learning, school districts have experimented with structured multimedia software programs that connect students with a deterministic learning task. An example represents *the Step-by-Step Digital Game-Based Program* to teach science in Uruguay. Therefore, the overt working definition of OLPC as

an unaffiliated provider of laptops to the poor and needy should observe that indirect, unofficial collaboration is definitely possible and even desirable to integrate the technology more seamlessly into the parameters of each given cultural context (Ezumah, 2010; Allen, 2012).

Consumers/Stakeholders of the OLPC program

According to the mission statement of OLPC, the official stakeholders and consumers of the project represented primary and secondary school children in developing countries. However, the project mobilized stakeholders and contributors from various industries and economic sectors, and critics argued that the emphasis on helping poor children has been possibly misleading and sanctimonious.

Allen (2012) observed that the program served Western technology interests more than the unique needs of developing countries, promoting the allied

hardware manufacturers, as Marvel and Google, over the target group. Other stakeholders were the design and research departments at MIT, including media activist Nicholas Negroponte and educator Seymore Pappert.

Macro-economically, the individuals most potentially affected and influenced were those who interacted with the children, as well as the citizens in the developing countries, whose tax contributions funded the OLPC program through their respective governments (Ezumah, 2010; Allen, 2012). Therefore, the overt mission and purpose to turn students into their own teachers and to empower their learning was a partial truth.

Increasing Benefits, Reducing Risks

Holm-Hansen (2007) emphasized a need to optimize benefits and minimize risks within the scope of an evaluation. OLPC would lend itself as an exemplary project upon which to apply and test this

essential ethical principle.

Related critics stressed the unbalanced, de-prioritized nature of the OLPC project; some low-income communities in developing countries have neither running water, electricity, nor adequately usable streets. In such areas, resource and priority should allocate to alleviate drastic deficits within the existing infrastructure, investing in OLPC once the conditions for a reasonable implementation have been met.

Since low-income participants frequently live in troubled, makeshift conditions, evaluators must strive to preserve participants' public perception and relocate endangered participants to an optimal research venue. Some traumatized participants may decline interviews regarding their past or certain discreet experiences, as such confidential conversations may reignite or aggravate emotional distress.

Cultural Competence

Schwandt (2007) advocated for an ethical program

evaluation that builds and acknowledges cultural competence for issues latent in the OLPC program. This critic observed that any effective, ethical program evaluation that involves diverse cultural encounters requires a sensitivity to unique perspectives and practices.

Such an emphasis on ethics requires an expansion of one's cultural knowledge and awareness to improve relations and promote diversity, empathy, and emotional intelligence. Empathy would enable the culturally competent program evaluator to put himself or herself into the shoes of a person from the other culture and to become an intelligent reader of someone else's story.

This perspective yields insight into the values, norms, and practices that shape the original, pilot evaluation program, enabling the OLPC evaluator to retool those variables for a more genuine, competent interaction with the target culture. Schwandt (2007) observed the importance to

balance a global perspective and a global agenda for sustainability with the local priorities and with the realities of any given indigenous culture. This balance would emerge optimally from a constructive, ongoing dialogue between and among different cultures, forging agreements and overcoming conflicts. One should avoid an effort to adjust aggressively to a different culture or to remain

passively neutral and objective:

“This cultural dialogue model for behaving ethically and for reaching agreement on a common ethical stance is premised on the assumption that one searches for understandings, beliefs, practices, admonitions, and the like that both resemble and challenge one’s own beliefs, values, and perspectives” (Schwandt, 2007).

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